

Low-Code Software Development in Healthcare Organizations: a Case Study from Italy

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25 March 2026

Abstract

Smaller healthcare organizations often do not have a software development team; therefore, when the software market does not offer suitable solutions for specific requests, the organizations must adapt or externalize a custom software development, and both those options come to a high cost. In this report, we present a case study from a healthcare organization in Italy which successfully applied a low-code development approach requiring few FTEs with the skillset of a data analyst (basic understanding of programming, strong analytical mindset) rather than of a software developer.

1 Introduction

Challenges about data management in healthcare organizations include the vast variety of the different software that are employed and the difficulties in data harmonization, and the lack of applications personalization and their portability [1, 2, 3].

Considering that the core business of healthcare organizations is to provide healthcare services, they seldom have software development teams unless they are integrated into bigger organizations and / or universities[4, 5]. The same applies for a wider implementation of the Agile methodology [6, 3].

Therefore, development of custom software would require so far unbudgeted costs linked to the creation of a development team, hosting, and certification; and if on one hand this would bring added value on very specific issues, on the other hand it would increase the “background noise” of unintegrated data.

In this landscape, one convenient way for smaller healthcare organizations to bring along software development, and thus implementing software customization and tests, is to resource the low code approach with the aim to produce working prototypes.

2 Low Code Approach and Prototyping

The Low-No Code Development (LNCD) approach enables non-developers to build software in a development environment mainly consisting of UI-based platforms that allow them to visually build applications (by placing screen elements) or create automation flows (by placing action blocks). It comes with limitations such as limited customization, scalability and dependency on the vendor policies [7, 8, 2].

LNCD has been consistently regarded as a mean to speed up development and delivery by 5-10 times [9, 4, 10]; but it can be used for fast development of applications that can be used as prototypes that can guide the choice of third-party software.

The availability of LNCD platforms makes then possible also for healthcare organizations without an internal development team to quickly build and deploy customized applications and / or prototypes[5, 3]. One employee with a basic understanding of coding and a strong analytical mindset (typical skills of a good data analyst) might be able to develop one or more interlinked applications for the benefit of the organization.

3 LNCD for the hospitalization management process

In the present study it will be reported the experience of a private healthcare organization with public accreditation, Gruppo Synergo, based in Pescara (Italy) and managing 8'000+ hospitalizations per year, which needed to streamline the data flow coming from the hospitalizations proposals into the operating theater planning and inpatient planning.

Among the LNCD available, it was decided to use the Microsoft Power Platform[11]. given its compliance to the GDPR and its integration in the Microsoft Office 365 package. Both platforms are available under licensing given by Microsoft.

Within the Microsoft Power Platform, the main development was conducted on Microsoft Power Apps (a low-code tool for UI app development) and Microsoft Power Automate (a low-code tool for data flow automation). In detail, in Microsoft Power Apps UI elements are placed visually while their be-

havior is largely determined by user-written code in the Power FX programming language. Applications developed in Microsoft Power Apps are accessible via web browser and via the Microsoft Power Apps application for mobile devices.

The first MVP prototype, developed and deployed by 1 FTE with the skillset of a data analyst and without formal training as software developer in approximately 6 weeks of time, consisted of:

- Hospitalization Proposal (HP) module: a form developed on Microsoft Forms, filled by the MD responsible for the hospitalization, containing the patient's personal data and the details of the proposed hospitalization and, when needed, of the proposed surgery. Through a data flow developed with Microsoft Power Automate, data are transferred to a Microsoft SharePoint list (a tool acting as a rough database, with the possibility of applying data types for columns and supplying row metadata such as row ID and creation and last edit timestamps) and a report in PDF is produced and sent to the MD via email.
- Operating Theater Planning (OTP) module: after confirming data with the patients, the dedicated administrative staff would transfer the data (with manual data entry) from the HP DB to the OTP module, a UI web app developed with Microsoft Power Apps that allows the planning of the operating theaters by allocating the patients in their surgery slot. Patients that are not undergoing surgery are registered separately in the app, that also calculates an estimation of the revenue generated by each hospitalization, according to the compensation schemas of the Servizio Sanitario Nazionale (SSN, the Italian NHS). OTP data is stored in Microsoft SharePoint with a direct table connection.
- Inpatient Planning (IP) module: OTP DB data, including specialty, estimated hospitalization duration and start date are shared with the IP module, which is also a UI web app developed with Microsoft Power Apps. The IP module allows management of 200+ bed places in 5 wards across 2 facilities, including dates management, bed transfer, and planning of incoming patients. IP data is stored in Microsoft SharePoint with a direct table connection.

This solution successfully managed 30,000+ hospitalizations in 4 years between 2022 and 2025 and, beyond giving the opportunity of refining the data flow process, it served as a prototype for highlighting the organization needs in terms of hospitalization management software. Since the market did not offer a suitable solution, at the end of 2025 it was decided to completely re-develop the prototype thus producing a final product. This process required 2,5 FTEs (still with the skillset of a data analyst and without formal training as software developer) worth workload across approximately 15 weeks of time:

- newly-developed Occupation Forecasting (OF) module: planning tool, developed on Microsoft Power Apps, which

uses data from the OTP and IP DBs to forecast the inpatient wards occupation for the upcoming future.

- newly-developed Recommended Exams (RE) module: developer on Microsoft Power Apps, it allows the MD to forward to exams booking staff a list of recommended exams for a patient. The booking staff will then contact the patient to propose opportunities to undergo those exams at the organization's facilities.
- newly-developed Outpatient Reporting (OR) module: aimed for the outpatient practices that don't rely on RIS and PACS systems, this application, developed on Microsoft Power Apps, allows the MD to write outpatient visits reports, print formatted versions in PDF (created with Microsoft Power Automate) and store them in a secure personal folder located in the Microsoft SharePoint document hosting tool. The worklist is hosted as a Microsoft SharePoint list and is renewed daily through a Microsoft Power Apps that synchronize extraction reports from third-party software (without direct DB query possibility) used for outpatient visits bookings. It also integrates the RE module.
- re-developed HP module: developed on Microsoft Power Apps rather than in Microsoft Forms, beyond the features already present in the MVP, automatic association with the logged MD, their specialty and their équipe; selection of diagnosis and procedure codes within a searchable ICD-9 (the standard still used by the SSN) catalogue; scanning of the barcode present on the Tessera Sanitaria (TS, the Italian personal tax code card, analogous to the USA's social security number card) to retrieve the tax code (feature available only when used on mobile, relying on the devices' camera); integration of the RE module; connection with the OR module; access to the whole personal history of HP with related statistics.
- newly-developed Private Patients Quoting Management (PPQM) module: among the patients entered in the HP module, the ones that want to go on privately (vs the opportunity to proceed within the SSN convention) will need to receive a quotation for the service. The PPQM module allows the user to create the quotation document to send to the patient by analyzing the past costs of similar hospitalizations, enabling custom calculations, creating the quotation in PDF (via Microsoft Power Automate), sending it to the patient via email with a pre-filled email body template and managing the patient's response.
- re-developed OTP module: this version, still developed on Microsoft Power Apps, includes as new features direct data connection with the HP DB, automated sending of information email to patients, contact attempts tracking, RE module history for the patient, PPQM module data access, improved usability and integrated with the OF module.
- re-developed IP module: a complete redesign of the previous version, still developed on Microsoft Power Apps,

that drastically improves the UX and integrates the OF module.

The biggest impact of these projects lies in the total control of data flow, from entry to analysis.

4 Overcoming Microsoft Power Platform's Customization Limitations

As stated previously, one downside of LNCD platforms is the limitations in customizations[12]. During the development of the aforementioned applications, the following limitations of the Microsoft Power Platform required elaborated solutions:

- 2 minutes timeout for Microsoft Power Automate flows: a flow connected to an app developed in Microsoft Power Apps must respond within 2 minutes otherwise the connection will go on timeout and the answer will not be transmitted to the app. This limit was not solvable in any way; therefore, the only solution here is to optimize flows to be executed within this limit.
- 2000 rows limit: for direct table connection between any source and Microsoft Power Apps, there is a 2000 rows limit. This is by far the most impactful limitations we encountered. The approach used was to keep tables under 2000 rows when applicable (automatically archiving a number of older-created rows via a Microsoft Power Automate flow: in our case, we chose to archive 200 rows when the table goes over 1900 rows, based on a daily check); when not applicable (e.g. when needing to retrieve the whole archive or for advanced privacy configuration, see next point), it was needed to retrieve data via a Microsoft Power Automate flow that gives back a JSON version of the requested table (possibly with filters in the query if needed), work that JSON inside the app and store it as a table in a collection (a collection is a table stored temporarily and locally during the execution of an application developed on Microsoft Power Apps). This process works - given the 2 minutes limit - but using collections rather than direct table connections impacts on data reading/writing time[10] and makes it impossible to harness the power of some optimized solutions like the view/edit forms inside Microsoft Power Apps.
- Lack of advanced privacy configuration for directly connected tables: when directly connecting a table to an application developed on Microsoft Power Apps, that table must be accessible to all the app users. This makes it impossible to apply the direct connection when the table contains sensitive data that only cannot be shared entirely with the users (e.g. a list of proposed hospitalizations; every MD should be able to see only their proposals and not all the proposals). As for the previous point, the solution here is to get the table in JSON via a Microsoft Power Automate flow (which can run on the flow's developer credentials, i.e. the table to read must be accessible to the developer only).

- Lack of a reliable PDF conversion: Microsoft Power Apps has implemented a PDF conversion tool that makes a screenshot of the current screen and then converts it to a PDF document. While this solution can be sufficient for some applications, it revealed to be sub-optimal for this case. It is possible to create a PDF document on Microsoft OneDrive via a Microsoft Power Automate flow by converting an HTML file (CSS can also be included). Therefore, it is possible to create fully formatted PDF documents starting from data inserted, generated or retrieved on a Microsoft Power Apps application by inserting the data into a CSS/HTML template (implementation of images is also possible, if converted to base64), passing this to a flow that will create a HTML file, convert it to PDF, and give back to the app the link to the final document.
- Lack of a printing on paper feature: while we strongly discouraged our users from printing on paper, it is sometimes needed. Microsoft Power Apps does not supply such a feature; the strategy here is to create HTML (usually well read by browsers) or PDF files as discussed earlier and instruct the users to print those.

5 Expansions

Beyond the applications described above, this approach was used for several smaller projects to govern the data flow. Here follows a brief list of other applications developed by Gruppo Synergo within the Microsoft Power Platform.

Apps already deployed:

- Operating Theaters monitoring: a simple read-only real-time monitor of the planning performed on the OTP app, mainly used on mobile devices by the authorized users (MDs and nurses).
- Ophthalmological surgery monitoring: simple ophthalmological surgeries (e.g. cataract removal) are planned directly from HP, without passing through the OTP app. Therefore, a monitor for the scheduled surgeries was needed.
- Internal teleconsulting platform: an application to schedule appointments for internal consulting, enable it via videocall and securely share documents and create compliant reports.
- Thoracic surgery teleprehabilitation: an application to register patients who need prehabilitation for thoracic surgery and then supplying them daily with a schedule and videoguide on how to perform the prehabilitation exercises autonomously[13].

Apps awaiting deployment:

- Pre-hospitalization anesthesiology assessment televisit: during pre-hospitalization assessment, the anesthesiology visit usually comes for last and after a long waiting time for the majority of low-risk patients. This app, connected to a

digitalized anamnestic questionnaire, enables the scheduling and delivering a televisit under certain conditions[14].

- Clinical diary for patients that will be followed with telemonitoring: an application to collect composite clinical data for patients currently hosted in inpatient wards but that will be telemonitored after they discharge, implementing the telemonitoring data as well and using LLMs to help the clinicians with the monitoring.

Moreover, it is possible to enrich all these apps with the following features that can be implemented on Microsoft Power Automate via subscription of a Premium account:

- External DB connection: beyond the already discussed Microsoft SharePoint lists, it is also possible to connect to relational DB engines such as MySQL, SQL, etc.
- LLM connection: both for external services reachable via API or locally-hosted ones (preferred under the GDPR).
- Document signature: implement verified digital signatures for MD reports.

6 Conclusions

This experience proved to be successful overall: the initial objective (governing the whole data flow) was fully achieved within the allocated time. The LNCD approach showed several advantages:

- Idea-to-deployment speed: it is possible to go from the initial idea to the first functioning MVP in 2 weeks or less.
- GDPR compliance: guaranteed by the vendor (Microsoft in this case) both for data flow and authentication.
- Ease of training: LNCD is quite intuitive and easily apprehensible by people with basic understanding of programming/coding. In our experience, in 4 weeks a resource is completely formed.
- Reliability: under 1% of flow failures in normal conditions, excluding global vendor outages that were in the order of 1 per year in the past 4 years.
- Flexibility: adding a new feature can be easily implemented within much less time despite the typical request made to a third-party software supplier.
- Mobile deployment: all the applications developed in Microsoft Power Apps are available on mobile devices.

Alongside some disadvantages:

- Technical limitations: the ones discussed above.
- Dependency on vendor: this is the most impactful liability of LNCD platforms. The vendor can unilaterally decide to cut services or tools, raise prices, or even discontinue everything. Moreover, vendors' outages will impact the

whole platform[15]. Finally, in the specific case of Microsoft, direct assistance is not given to smaller clients, but it is mediated by other suppliers that may or may not be adequately prepared on lesser-spread tools like the Power Platform.

Economic quantification was conducted using an extended cost-benefit framework incorporating system-level organizational effects, consistent with Health Technology Assessment (HTA) methodologies[16], and a related article is currently in the making. The model includes three components:

- Direct economic impact: the implementation of low-code digital solutions generated substantial cost savings compared to market alternatives (estimated €500k+ avoided over 5 years), along with efficiency gains corresponding to approximately 10,000 hours of recovered clinical time (~€300k) and increased surgical activity, with an estimated additional revenue potential of ~€1.6M over 5 years. This impact increased its organizational value with the increasing saturation of production facilities, ergo, the secondary impact on operational efficiency is superlinear in time.
- Operational efficiency: process optimization and digital workflow integration led to measurable improvements in hospital efficiency, including reduced errors (less postponed or cancelled surgical interventions, better accountability at each step of the care process, etc.) and improved patient flow (increased number of patient pre-hospitalization, much higher operating time versus non-operating time in the OR, etc.). Notably, in the past 3 years the bed utilization increased in the secondary facility, with a +2% rise in rehabilitation wards and +5% in medical wards. Even marginal increases in bed occupancy are known to produce disproportionate gains in system capacity and productivity[17], and in 2026 the estimated impact through stochastic simulation will be even higher, approximating the theoretical maximum occupancy. These findings are consistent with evidence showing that digital health technologies improve efficiency and generate positive returns on investment[18].
- System-level financial impact: the reorganization of clinical activities at the surgical hub (primary facility) enabled a capacity reallocation effect across facilities sharing the same clinical workforce, increasing overall system productivity. This improved efficiency allows the secondary facility to reach ordinary budget thresholds and unlock additional high-specialty funding, estimated at €400,000 over the 2025–2026 period. Optimized patient flow and resource allocation are known to significantly impact both costs and quality of care[19].

7 Funding

The first two authors acknowledge financial support from the Strengthening of research structures and creation of R&D “In-

novation Ecosystems”, National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.5, funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – VITALITY, ECS00000041 (grant no. D73C22000840006).

8 Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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